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Societal Impact of Transdisciplinary and Participatory Research: A Guide for Assessment

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The Guide for Assessment (Part I) was developed by the team of authors as part of the AG Wirkung (Impact Working Group) of the Society for Transdisciplinary and Participatory Research (GTPF). The three application examples in Part II were written by individual authors.

www.gtpf.science

SOCIETAL IMPACT OF TRANSDISCIPLINARY AND PARTICIPATORY RESEARCH: A GUIDE FOR ASSESSMENT

Transdisciplinary and participatory research (TDPR) is characterised by its intention to achieve not only scientific but also societal impact. This raises the questions: What is societal impact? How can the impact potential of TDPR be assessed? In an interdisciplinary team, we have developed a guide that identifies criteria and exemplary indicators for assessing societal effects and impact potential in TDPR (Part I). The guide contributes to systematising the range of criteria of societal effects and supports the operationalisation of these criteria for evaluation and monitoring. In addition to criteria for direct effects (outcome) and indirect effects (impact), we also list criteria for process quality, as these have a significant influence on the generation of impact potential in TDPR.

The guide is intended to enable researchers from different disciplines and (research) communities to identify different types of effects that are relevant for their respective research projects and develop appropriate evaluation and monitoring concepts. For formative evaluation, it also supports reflection on one's own approaches to assessing societal effects of TDPR, as well as on the potential and limitations of impact evaluation.

Part II provides examples from three research fields - citizen science, participatory health research and transdisciplinary research on sustainable urban development - to illustrate the applicability of the guide across diverse TDPR domains.

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Introduction

This document is the product of a collaboration between researchers of the Working Group on Societal Impact at the German Society for Transdisciplinary and Participatory Research (GTPF¹). The work process involved researchers from different fields of transdisciplinary and participatory research (TDPR), such as health, sustainability, innovation, citizen science and urban research². In these research fields, representatives of various interests and perspectives (e.g. actors from administration, business and civil society, citizens, patients) cooperate based on the assumption that the co-production of knowledge is key to making a significant contribution to understanding and solving urgent and complex societal problems. The authors share the view that reflecting on potential societal effects and tracing or recording generated or expected outcomes and impacts makes it possible to determine whether TDPR actually makes this contribution. In doing so, TDPR researchers are also responding to demands from social actors in politics, business, civil society and research funding, who are increasingly calling for evidence of the assumed societal benefits and scientific added value of these research approaches (Kopfmüller et al. 2024, Bühner et al. 2022).

This guide focuses on how the range of different *societal* effects of TDPR can be systematised and operationalised for evaluation and monitoring purposes. Another working paper of the GTPF Impact Working Group deals with the scientific effects of TDPR (Theiler et al. 2025). The participants in both working groups are aware that there are interactions between the societal

and scientific effects of TDPR, and that, in some cases, they cannot be clearly distinguished from one another. Evidence of this can also be found in the literature (Swedish Research Council 2021).

The group of authors assumes that raising awareness of the different impact categories of TDPR will strengthen the power to act and communication skills of those involved in the research process. The diverse effects of research projects can thus be better addressed in internal and external communication.

Well-evidenced statements on the effects that can be achieved through temporarily funded TDPR projects also enable dialogue with funding bodies and project sponsors on realistic requirements, as well as manage expectation among project partners involved in the research. We assume that reflecting on who perceives which effects as positive or negative, and taking unintended effects into account, contribute to the responsible implementation of research. It is also important to critically reflect on who is evaluating on whose behalf, and who determines which societal effects are (or should be) aimed for: the group of people involved in the TDPR process or the funding bodies, or clients. This may result in restrictions or consolidation of existing structures, exclusion practices, conflicts, and power relations that actually contradict the aims of TDPR.

It is therefore helpful to be aware that evaluation practice itself always plays a role as a governance instrument. For evaluations to be legitimate, transparency is crucial regarding how they are carried out, by whom, with what aim, and how the results will be used.

1 www.gtpf.science.de

2 The product is therefore based on work carried out by researchers without the involvement of other societal actors. It will be made available for broad discussion at a later stage. As evaluations are primarily carried out by scientists and professional evaluators, they are the main target group for the guide.

For example, the British Research Excellence Framework (REF) uses published case studies - evaluating the effects of research projects conducted up to 20 years ago - to decide about the allocation of funding to research institutions³. In contrast, the Strategy Evaluation Protocol in the Netherlands aims, among other things, to evaluate and further develop self-imposed strategies of research institutions with a view to their societal effects (de Jong & Spaapen 2023).

We would particularly like to highlight the similarity between the TDPR's understanding of societal impact and the concept of productive interactions (Spaapen & van Drooge 2011). The concept of productive interactions sees direct (e.g. via communication), indirect (e.g. via the publication of results) and financial interactions (e.g. via the allocation of funds) with the recipients of the research results as central to the development of outcomes and impacts. Interactions are considered productive if the addressees commit to using the results. Since impacts are often difficult to prove due to the existing time and attribution gap, some projects use the description of productive interactions as an approximation of expected impacts (e.g. Spaapen et al. 2011). In the present guide, we agree with the importance of interactions in the transdisciplinary and participatory research process for the emergence of societal effects and therefore also formulate criteria and indicators for process quality (see Section 3.1).

As transdisciplinary and participatory researchers, we are aware that the call for impactful research can also be viewed critically in terms of the openness of research results and the pressure to succeed that this entails. We believe that the involvement of societal actors in research processes has intrinsic value in terms of recognising the relevance of different forms of knowledge.

The results of participation and involvement processes are always open, and their effects cannot be "programmed". In addition to recording intended effects, it is essential to reflect on unintended and negative effects.

The guide for assessment is intended to support and inspire individuals involved in impact planning, reflection and assessment and in TDPR (see Chapter 1, Objectives and functions). The research teams involved should then operationalise the listed categories and dimensions (process quality, output, outcome, and impact), taking into account the specific characteristics of their respective research projects. Examples of this are presented in Part II. Joint reflection on adequate criteria and indicators supports the aim that the scientific and non-scientific participants of the projects agree on the desired results, societal effects, and central requirements for the quality of the research process (transparency, iterativeness, etc.).

The document comprises two parts. Part I contains a presentation of the guide and is structured as follows: Chapter 1 takes a closer look at the objectives and functions of the guide and the target groups. Chapter 2 defines the key terms. Chapter 3 contains a compilation of criteria and examples of indicators for operationalising three dimensions of impact: process quality, outcome, and impact. Chapter 4 discusses the methodological challenges of assessing societal effects.

Part II provides examples of how the guide can be applied in three research fields: citizen science, participatory health research and transdisciplinary urban research.

The document concludes with a reflection on future directions, information on the GTPF, and the list of references.

3 <https://2029.ref.ac.uk/>

PART I PRESENTATION OF THE GUIDE

1 OBJECTIVES, FUNCTIONS AND TARGET GROUPS OF THE GUIDE FOR ASSESSMENT

This guide for assessing the societal effects and impact potential of transdisciplinary and participatory research (TDPR) was developed in response to the growing demand for evidence of societal effects.

Many research teams face the same challenge of agreeing on meaningful categories for assessing outcome and impact. To facilitate this task, the core of this guide provides an overview of possible dimensions for assessing societal effects, including criteria and examples of indicators.

The participants have developed this paper with the following objective in mind: to provide an interdisciplinary guide for assessing societal effects that can be used by various research communities in an early stage, in order to strengthen the impact orientation of TDPR.

The authors share the view that both – the way in which the research process is designed and carried out, and the results (outputs) – have an influence on the societal effects that can be achieved in a research project and on the impact potential that can be realised.

The guide for assessment is intended to fulfil the following **functions**:

- Support in identifying the impact areas relevant to the respective research project. The breadth of the proposed dimensions and criteria should:
 - Provide ideas in which areas to "search" for societal effects and how to strengthen them;
 - Facilitate the development of evaluation and monitoring concepts for societal effects of transdisciplinary and participatory research – which affords a selection of appropriate criteria and indicators.
- Promote reflection on the approach taken in transdisciplinary and participatory research and on the link between research activities and the desired effects. This may include, for example, reflection on unintended/negative effects and the identification of potential conflicts as part of a formative evaluation (supporting accompanying research).
- Provide a basis for reflecting on the potential and limitations of evaluating the societal effects of transdisciplinary and participatory research and support appropriate expectation management vis-à-vis those involved in the process and funding bodies.

The guide for assessment can be used for evaluations that are prospective (ex ante), formative (accompanying) or summative (ex post).

In order to exploit the potential for iterative improvement of impact-oriented research activities by TDPR, the members of our working

group consider types of formative evaluation that support TDPR participants in their research activities to be particularly useful.

The target groups for using the orientation guide are both those involved in TDPR and external evaluators and funding providers.

The guide for assessment was developed with the intention that it can be used by diverse TDPR communities (e.g. transdisciplinary and transformative sustainability research, citizen science, participatory health and technology research, innovation research, urban research).

The presentation of the guide is only partly embedded in current debates on the challenges of impact assessment.

Furthermore, it does not aim to provide the following:

- A comprehensive discussion and examination of the usefulness of impact assessment in general
- A precise description of methods for impact assessment
- Examples of projects conducted with impact orientation in mind.⁴

⁴ Another group of the Impact Working Group works on the topic of impact-oriented project management (see <https://gtpf.science/>).

2 DEFINITIONS OF KEY TERMS

In this chapter, we would like to present the definitions of terms that are central to the guide and which the authors have agreed on.

This is a pragmatic agreement as a common denominator for the guide, which does not preclude the authors from using different definitions in their own research contexts.

The participants have agreed to adhere as closely as possible to definitions provided by recognised organisations (such as the German Evaluation Society (DeGEval)) in order to ensure broad compatibility and acceptance.

2.1 Terms for describing impact chains

(partly based on DeGEval 2016, *additions noted and printed in italics*)

Input

Resources: financial, human, material, administrative, organisational and other means invested in a programme/project/intervention to achieve its objectives (DeGEval 2016).

Activities

The work steps and activities carried out in the course of implementing an evaluation object (*addition: in our case, the transdisciplinary or participatory research process*) that serve to achieve results and effects, such as surveys, communication, coordination, reflection within the team, etc.

The DeGEval definitions of output, outcome and impact did not seem appropriate for our field of activity – transdisciplinary and participatory research. The definitions chosen are based on various sources.

Output

The tangible results of the transdisciplinary or participatory research process through which effects are to be achieved. Examples from our research practice, without claiming to be exhaustive, include:

- Exchange formats within the transdisciplinary or participatory research team or with other stakeholders, interested or affected parties (e.g. community events, stakeholder workshops, citizen dialogues, etc.)

- Organisation of or participation in events for the presentation and discussion of (preliminary) results with non-scientific actors (e.g. presentations at specialist events for practitioners)
- Practice-relevant publications of TDPR (preliminary) results and recommendations for action (e.g. policy papers, handbooks, guidelines, tool kits, etc.)
- Formats for science communication (e.g. podcasts, science slams)
- Target group-specific formats for imparting skills (e.g. further education, training, etc.)
- Prototypes of new products, models
- In real-world laboratories: experiments conducted to test solutions

Outcome

Short- and medium-term effects on those directly involved in TDPR (= direct effects). Outcomes occur within the temporal and spatial context of the research project. Inspired by Belcher et al. (2020), we assume that they can be specifically targeted by those involved in the research process (sphere of control).

Impact

Impact describes the longer-term effects of TDPR on society or parts of society that extend beyond the participants in the research process (science and practice) and the temporal and spatial context of TDPR.

Societal impact is therefore a combination of indirect effects resulting from the transdisciplinary or participatory research process and of the direct effects (outcome).

Inspired by Belcher et al. (2020), we distinguish between:

- effects over which the TDPR team has a certain influence, but which depend on the participation of other actors and suitable framework conditions (sphere of influence) and
- further effects in the respective field of action to which the project, as one of several actors, aims to contribute; however, direct attribution to the respective research project is not possible (sphere of interest).

The distinction between these categories along the impact chain is intended to facilitate mutual understanding. However, differences may arise depending on the project objectives. For example, networking can be understood as a direct outcome of activities such as workshops or project meetings involving participants. In some projects, however, establishing networks is a desired output, in which case it is also categorised as such.

It is also important to mention that direct effects (outcomes), such as learning processes or networks might be necessary for developing further outputs, such as formulating recommendations for action.

2.2 Other relevant terms

Transdisciplinary research

Transdisciplinarity is a reflexive, integrative, method-driven scientific principle that aims to solve or overcome societal problems and related scientific problems by differentiating and integrating knowledge from different scientific and social knowledge bases and transferring it to both scientific and social practice. Key features are:

- (a) Focus on socially relevant problems;
- (b) Enabling mutual learning processes between researchers from different disciplines and non-scientific actors;
- (c) The creation of knowledge that is solution-oriented, socially robust and transferable to scientific and social practice (Lang et al. 2012).

Participatory research

The term participatory research encompasses research approaches that aim to explore, understand and change social reality in partnership with others in order to contribute to the emancipation, social justice and democratisation of (marginalised) social groups. Thus, the participation of societal actors in a dual objective, reflecting on social, political and organisational contexts and thereby influencing them in a sustainable manner (Unger 2014).

Definitions from DeGEval 2016

(additions or changes in italics)

Impact

In general, changes that can be traced back to causes. In evaluations, the focus is usually on changes triggered directly or indirectly by the

→ evaluation object (*in our case, the transdisciplinary or participatory research process*) that are to be considered analytically separate from other causes. A distinction is often made between short-, medium- and long-term effects on target groups (→ outcomes) or on other persons, groups, institutions, systems, etc. (→ impacts).

Subject (of an evaluation):

The issue which is examined and assessed within the scope of the evaluation (*in our case, the transdisciplinary or participatory research process and its results*) and to which possible consequences of the evaluation refer to (purpose of an evaluation).

Target group (*of the evaluation*) Individuals, groups, institutions or other entities for which the evaluation object is intended to achieve its intended effects (in our case, the individuals, groups and institutions involved in the TDPR research process, as well as the individuals, groups and institutions that are additionally addressed by the activities and results).

Context

Factors in the environment of an evaluation object (*in our case, the transdisciplinary or participatory research process*) that can influence its implementation and effects (e.g. political, legal, organisational, social and cultural aspects or even current events).

Evaluation

The systematic investigation of the usefulness and/or quality of an object (→ evaluation object) on the basis of empirically obtained data. Implies an assessment based on disclosed → criteria for a specific purpose.

Ex-ante evaluation

Evaluation carried out before the implementation of a programme/research project/intervention on the basis of concepts, plans or proposals, assessing aspects such as need, feasibility or prospects of success. Ex-ante evaluation is a synonym for **prospective evaluation**. This term will be used throughout the rest of the text.

Formative evaluation

Evaluation that serves the purpose of improving and controlling the evaluation object (*in our case, improving the transdisciplinary or participatory research process and its results*). It is primarily aimed at (programme) managers and is usually carried out in parallel with the measure and often on a periodical basis.

Ex-post evaluation

Evaluation that assesses a programme (*research project, intervention*) retrospectively after its completion, whereby data collected before or during the implementation may also be included. The focus is often on sustainability and long-term effects. Ex-post evaluation is synonymous with **summative evaluation**. This terminology will be used throughout the rest of the text.

Monitoring

Routinely, regular and criteria-based collection and documentation of comparative data with the aim of identifying control requirements in due time. Unlike evaluation, monitoring does not involve assessment and is always designed as a longitudinal process.

2.3 Terms used to structure a list of criteria and indicators

Dimensions – Criteria – Indicators

Dimension

Superordinate category for systematising characteristics of the evaluation object (*in our case, the effects of the transdisciplinary or participatory research process*)

Criterion

Characteristic of an evaluation object (*in our case, the effects of the transdisciplinary or participatory research process*) whose quality or usefulness is determined by comparison with a target value, whereby an assessment is usually based on several criteria.

Indicator

Empirically measurable characteristic that makes a phenomenon that is not directly observable but is significant for the evaluation object accessible for qualitative or quantitative assessment.

3 CRITERIA AND INDICATORS

This chapter provides guidance on which criteria and indicators can be used to operationalise the dimensions of process quality, outcome and impact within the framework of evaluation or monitoring concepts for TDPR (see Chapter 1 Objectives and functions of the Guide for assessment).

When planning formative or summative evaluations, the challenge is to select suitable indicators for which data can be collected with reasonable effort for the respective research project. The spectrum ranges from more qualitative methods (such as interviews and observations) to the evaluation of documents and quantitative methods (surveys and measurement of specific parameters). The criteria and indicators can be used for reflective self-evaluation and readjustment of research goals, questions and methods and/or for the development of a monitoring concept.

The overview presented here is not a complete and exhaustive collection, but intends to provide inspiration. The criteria must be further specified and supported by appropriate indicators within the context of the respective research project, depending on the research question and objectives. The indicators listed here should therefore be understood as illustrative examples.

3.1 Process quality

This chapter provides an exemplary overview of criteria and indicators for the dimension "process quality". As described in the introduction, we assume that the quality of research processes – i.e. how cooperation in participatory and transdisciplinary processes is organised – is essential for achieving research impact. The conscious evaluation of the perceived quality of joint research and how results are communicated and disseminated, takes up the argumentation of "productive interactions" mentioned in the

introduction. Continuous monitoring allows adapting the process design in response to perceived deficits and weaknesses.

The criteria and indicators proposed here are based on publications from several scientific communities and approaches, which in some cases go to greater depth on individual aspects (including Unger 2014, Adamson & Howe 2015, Darby 2017, Oetzel et al. 2018, ICPHR 2020, Beeker 2021).

The indicators are formulated as questions. Some criteria are more suitable for quantitative evaluation (e.g. measures to ensure accessibility), while others are more suitable for qualitative evaluation procedures.

This operationalisation of the criteria provides questions about the quality of the research process, leaving room for more specific evaluation options, which always depend on disciplinary requirements, resources, etc.

All questions are formulated in the past tense for the purposes of a summative evaluation. This is not intended to exclude prospective and formative approaches – on the contrary: all questions can be used for continuous reflection both during the planning and in the course of a research project.

Many of the criteria become relevant repeatedly at different points during the course of a research project. For example, the precise definition of objectives should be an ongoing topic, because objectives and expectations are often implicit at the beginning of a research process and sometimes only become concrete or explicit in the course of collaboration.

The first criterion, "power to act", is of overarching importance to us: we consider enabling or delegating power to be fundamental to ensuring equal participation and transdisciplinary collaboration.

Dimension: Process Quality

CRITERIA	INDICATORS
Power to act	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Has the power to act been (re)distributed? → Was decision-making power shared? → Were bottom-up processes possible?
Inclusivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were necessary measures taken to ensure accessibility? → Were representatives of all relevant stakeholder groups able to participate/contribute? → Was attention paid to the diversity of the participants' backgrounds in terms of life experience and knowledge (e.g. gender, age, socio-economic background, etc.)? → Was the work carried out in a language that was accessible to everyone?
Integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Are the issues addressed of interest or relevance to all participants? → Were all relevant forms of knowledge (research and practice) included? → Were the different perspectives/forms of knowledge linked in order to develop system-oriented solutions? → Were (all) actors from the relevant fields of action involved at an early stage?
Transparency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Was (limited) scope for action (e.g. due to the type of funding allocation) communicated? → Were roles and expertise clearly defined/communicated? → Were expectations communicated (on an ongoing basis)? → Were contact persons and responsibilities clear to everyone? → Were the objectives of the project and the interests of the individual participants clearly stated? → Were decision-making criteria and processes clearly outlined? → Were the methods used in the project clearly communicated to promote the traceability of the results and confidence in them? → Were uncertainties in the level of knowledge and complex interrelationships openly explained during the course of the project?
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were there defined channels for two-way communication with/from the project management? → Were communication channels or media provided for exchange among project participants? → Were the communication channels accessible to everyone without barriers? → Was planning done in advance so that all participants could be involved with sufficient notice and receive feedback on their contributions? → Did all project participants have access to knowledge relevant to the project and to the insights generated by the project?

Dimension: Process Quality

CRITERIA	INDICATORS
Definition of objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were differing definitions of objectives possible/were conflicting objectives made visible? → Were non-academic objectives also taken into account? → Were the intended effects aimed for the practitioners reflected on at an early stage? → Were possible negative effects and risks reflected on at an early stage? → Was the research project aligned with the needs and expectations of the future users of the results?
Adaptability / Iterativity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Was the research process open/flexible enough to allow for co-determination? → Were those involved sufficiently open to change? → Was there sufficient room for feedback/exchange/comments? → Were there opportunities to document and reflect on unexpected development? → Were uncertainties in the knowledge base and complex interrelationships taken into account during the course of the project?
Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Did the project offer opportunities for different forms of learning? → Were power imbalances between participants reflected upon? → Was the process experienced as appreciative by all participants? → Were emotions allowed during the collaboration and were they tolerated? → Did the process enable the development of mutual trust and understanding? → Were different time logics taken into account? → Was there an attitude that allowed for learning from mistakes? → Were structurally determined inequalities in opportunities and resources reflected upon or compensated for?
Clarification of outputs/outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Did the project benefit all participants and were these benefits reasonably balanced? → Were different outputs promoted for different target groups? → Was there sufficient space for negotiating authorship and questions of ownership?
Dissemination of results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were the requirements of the target groups taken into account in the type of outputs? (target group-appropriate language, formats, scope, relevance to action) → Was there collaboration with representatives of the target group (e.g. multipliers) to disseminate results? → Was the dissemination of results actively promoted? (e.g. presentations, references in newsletters, social media) → Were results made permanently freely accessible? (open access, etc.)

3.2 Outcome

In this chapter, we provide an exemplary list of criteria and indicators for the dimension "outcome".

Outcome describes the short- and medium-term effects of transdisciplinary and participatory research that occur directly among those involved in the research process (science and practice) and in the temporal and spatial context of TDPR. Outcomes are largely controllable (sphere of control).

Here, too, the exemplary list of criteria and indicators draws on concepts from various scientific communities and traditions, such as social learning processes (Batz & Ehnert 2023, Van Poeck et al. 2020), (dis)empowerment (Avelino et al. 2023), leverage points (Abson et al. 2017, Meadows 1999), approaches to systematising societal effects in transdisciplinary research (Mogalle 2001, Schäfer et al. 2021, Walter et al. 2007) and applied research (Moser & Wolf 2023, Wolf et al. 2024).

Furthermore, there are interactions between the criteria. Learning processes in particular are considered important process elements for promo-

ting further changes such as the development of new practices or the adaptation of institutions and infrastructures. New insights can be gained from observing these dynamics.

With regard to the operationalisation of learning processes, we refer to the systematisation according to three types of knowledge that are distinguished in transdisciplinary research (ProClim 1997, Pohl & Hirsch Hadorn 2008).

System knowledge is described as "knowledge about what is", target knowledge as "knowledge about what should and should not be" and transformation knowledge as "knowledge about how we get from the present state to the envisioned state" (ibid.).

While system knowledge encompasses the understanding of interrelationships and dynamics in socio-ecological systems, target knowledge refers to the scientifically based understanding of normative objectives in various fields of action, and transformation knowledge refers to the development of concrete actionable knowledge.

Dimension: Outcome – Sphere of Control

CRITERIA	EXEMPLARY INDICATORS
Promotion of learning processes (cognitive, normative)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognition and integration of plural forms of knowledge, such as everyday and experiential knowledge, indigenous knowledge, marginalised perspectives/knowledge bases • System knowledge (analytical): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Expansion of knowledge about characteristics, dynamics and cause-and-effect relationships in socio-ecological, socio-technical and socio-institutional systems ▪ Development of a common problem understanding • Target knowledge (normative) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Shared understanding of guiding principles and visions for the future ▪ Change in attitudes, values and preferences ▪ Change in role understanding (individual and organisational) • Transformation knowledge (actionable knowledge): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mutual learning: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Mutual learning about perspectives, rationales for action and needs of others – Development of a common understanding of options for action in the respective field of research ▪ Capacity building: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – E.g. skills for reflection and co-creation of knowledge, learning TDPR methods – Promotion of scientific literacy/understanding of scientific processes – Empathy and conflict mediation skills – Practical skills (e.g. taking and analysing water samples, repairing, processing local fruit varieties)
Strengthening social relationships and cooperation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network building • Building trust and mutual understanding, including for differences • Community building and development of collective identities • Development of strategic contacts
Strengthening reputation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening individual reputation • Strengthening organisational reputation
Emotional changes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experience of self-efficacy (e.g. change in self-image and self-esteem) • Change in motivation

Dimension: Outcome – Sphere of Control

CRITERIA	EXEMPLARY INDICATORS
Strengthening empowerment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expanding resources and capacities to act (e.g. financial resources, space) • Being heard and recognised with one's own perspectives and positions • Strengthening one's own power to act through collaboration and networking with "like-minded people" (e.g. citizens in citizen science, cooperation between patients)
Changes in actions and practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiences with disrupting routines and trying out new practices in various fields of action (e.g. mobility, nutrition, health care and treatment) • Changes in organisational practices
Institutional changes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Temporary) institutional changes (e.g. new positions, areas of responsibilities) • Changes in governance (e.g. more participation and co-creation, changes in regulations)
Infrastructural changes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Temporary) changes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Built infrastructure (e.g. settlement structures and buildings, road space) ▪ Green and blue infrastructure (e.g. green spaces, water) ▪ Technical infrastructure (e.g. energy, transport, ICT, digitalisation)

3.3 Impact

In this chapter, we provide an exemplary list of criteria and indicators for the dimension "impact". Impact refers to the longer-term effects of TDPR on society or parts of society that extend beyond those involved in the research process (research and practice) and the temporal and spatial context of TDPR. These are indirect effects that evolve from the transdisciplinary or participatory research process and its direct effects (outcome).

Inspired by Belcher et al. (2020), we distinguish between:

- Effects over which the TDPR team has a certain influence, but which depend on the participation of other actors and supportive contextual conditions (sphere of influence).

- Further effects in the respective field of action to which the TDPR team - as one actor among many - would like to contribute; however, direct attribution of these effects to the respective research project is not possible (sphere of interest).

The proposals for criteria and indicators draw on various concepts such as leverage points (Abson et al. 2017, Meadows 1999), (dis)empowerment (Avelino et al. 2023), approaches to systematising societal impacts in transdisciplinary research (Mogalle 2001, Schäfer et al. 2021, Walter et al. 2007) and applied research (Moser & Wolf 2023, Wolf et al. 2024), ecosystem services (Haines-Young et al. 2009), the sustainability assessment of agricultural and food systems (SAFA Guidelines) (FAO 2013) and the work of the DeGEval Ad Hoc Group on Sustainability (2024).

It should be noted that there are interactions between the phenomena underlying the criteria. Knowledge transfer and knowledge integration are considered particularly important process elements for promoting further transformation processes such as changes in discourse or the

establishment of new practices and routines. In addition, changes in practices often form the basis for economic, ecological and social effects, and these effects should therefore be considered together. Observing these dynamics can generate new insights.

Dimension: Impact – Sphere of Influence

CRITERIA	EXEMPLARY INDICATORS
Continuation and expansion of activities and practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the project context: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Follow-up projects (from own resources or via funding bodies) • Transfer to other temporal and spatial contexts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Follow-up projects in other contexts ▪ Implementation of project results in other contexts ▪ Extension of modified practices to other stakeholder groups
Expansion and deepening of cooperation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of new (strategic) contacts and partnerships (e.g. with intermediaries and multipliers, decision-makers at various levels and in various institutional contexts) • Establishment of new networks and communities of practice (e.g. practice-research networks) • Institutionalisation and professionalisation of networks
Knowledge transfer and acquisition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge transfer beyond the project context to other temporal and spatial contexts (e.g. through the involvement of intermediaries and multipliers, target group-oriented events and publications)

Dimension: Impact – Sphere of Interest (TDPR aims to make a contribution)

CRITERIA	EXEMPLARY INDICATORS
Change in knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of new/changed paradigms and concepts (e.g. sustainable urban development, regenerative agriculture, new understandings of "illness and health") • Recognition and integration of plural forms of knowledge • Integration of knowledge into practices, research, teaching and practical infrastructures, institutions and discourses • Changed training content
Establishment of new/changed practices and routines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • E.g. of health maintenance, care, nutrition, mobility, consumption, energy production, construction, urban planning

Dimension: Impact – Sphere of Interest (TDPR aims to make a contribution)

CRITERIA	EXEMPLARY INDICATORS
Establishment of new/changed discourses and narratives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of new/changed world views, values and concepts (e.g. paradigm shifts, understanding of health and prevention, role of science in society)
Establishment of new/changed institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of new/changed forms of decision-making and governance in research and practice (e.g. participatory and co-creative decision-making, more decentralised and power-sensitive cooperation) • Establishment of new/changed regulations and laws • Establishment of new/changed organisational units (e.g. sustainability department, prevention department) • Establishment of new/changed role profiles and forms of expertise (e.g. positions, facilitators, knowledge brokers, change in the understanding of the role of science as an institution) • Establishment of a new/changed management and collaboration culture in organisations (removal of barriers and improvement of accessibility) • Establishment of institutions to continue project activities (e.g. establishment of real-world laboratories and/or funding guidelines and programmes, support for collaborative working groups)
Establishment of new/changed infrastructures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Built infrastructure (e.g. settlement structures and buildings) • Green and blue infrastructure (e.g. green spaces, water) • Technical infrastructure (e.g. energy, transport, ICT, digitalisation) • Removal of barriers and/or improvement of accessibility
Transformation of power relations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening participation and social inclusion • Changed distribution of decision-making authority and power to act (e.g. participatory decision-making structures) • Changed distribution of resources (e.g. finances, financial support for practice partners) • Changed access to and distribution of knowledge and skills (e.g. open access, public libraries)

Dimension: Impact – Sphere of Interest (T DPR aims to make a contribution)

CRITERIA	EXEMPLARY INDICATORS
Economic effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of (technological and social) innovations, e.g. new/changed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Business models and economic forms (e.g. shift from profit orientation to public welfare orientation, fair trade) ▪ Goods or products (e.g. recyclable materials) ▪ Services (e.g. in the areas of repair, recycling, sharing) ▪ Business and production processes (e.g. distribution and logistics, information and communication) • Securing livelihoods, i.e. satisfying basic needs, e.g. food, energy, housing, mobility, health • Building or strengthening resilient economic structures, e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Security of supply ▪ Regional value creation ▪ Diversification of products, markets and business areas ▪ Transparent supply chains ▪ Circular economy • Social responsibility and good governance, e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fair income distribution ▪ Compliance with employee rights, occupational safety and health protection
Ecological effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate • Adaptation to climate change • Preservation or enhancement of biodiversity • Preservation or regeneration of natural resources (e.g. water, soil, air) • Minimisation of pollutants (e.g. air, water, soil) • Resource and energy efficiency (e.g. waste prevention, recycling, durability and reparability of products) • Use of renewable resources • Strengthening ecosystem services: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Provisioning services ▪ Regulating and maintenance services: climate, air, water, soil, diseases ▪ Cultural services (e.g. strengthening recreational functions)

Dimension: Impact – Sphere of Interest (T DPR aims to make a contribution)

CRITERIA	EXEMPLARY INDICATORS
Societal effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening social cohesion • Strengthening social justice, e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Poverty reduction ▪ Equal opportunities (gender equality, non-discrimination and promotion of diversity, inclusion, reconciliation of family and working life) • Promoting access to, for example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Education ▪ Health services • Improving the quality of life and opportunities, especially for socially disadvantaged groups (e.g. health, well-being and self-care)

4 METHODOLOGICAL CHALLENGES IN MEASURING IMPACT

Measuring impact in a transdisciplinary and participatory research setting poses a number of methodological challenges. The problem of causality and attribution (attribution problem) of impacts is a key challenge and highlights the fact that it is often impossible to establish clear causal links between research activities and societal effects using methodological means (Schäfer & Lux 2020, Spaapen and van Drooge 2011, Bornmann 2013). The main reasons for this are that transdisciplinary and participatory research does not take place in a controlled laboratory setting and usually without a control group, and that effects often occur with a time lag and in other (spatial) contexts.

The effects of transdisciplinary and participatory research are primarily the result of complex communication and exchange processes (Kaufmann-Hayoz et al. 2016). As a rule, statements can only be made about direct effects within the group of participants. Further effects, such as the preservation of biodiversity, the improvement of living or working conditions, the concrete contribution to sustainable mobility and urban development, etc., cannot usually be attributed to individual research projects, as there are numerous other influencing factors that cannot be controlled, managed or monitored.

Therefore, with regard to further effects, statements can generally only be made about plausibly

expected effects, i.e. impact potential. In the context of a prospective evaluation, which primarily identifies needs and anticipated effects, the problem of estimating foreseeable causalities and attributing effects is particularly evident. However, this does not mean that prospective evaluation is of little importance, as it can contribute to realistic and reflective management, better communication between the various parties involved and a better learning process within the teams.

There is a certain overlap here with formative evaluation, which is primarily carried out with the aim of promoting learning processes and improvements during the course of the project (van Drooge & Spaapen 2022). Although these tie up the capacities of the actors, they also have the potential to have an integrating effect. Evaluators in their role as translators bring together different perspectives of those involved in the project and ask questions about mechanisms of action, thereby facilitating knowledge integration and contributing to the respective research field (Wiefek et al. 2024; see also dialogue function according to Stockmann 2004).

Summative evaluations often fulfil the function of result-oriented assessments. This encompasses the problem that delayed effects may not yet have occurred at the time of analysis, and that it is hardly possible to clearly assign the effects to their causes.

In addition to the causality and attribution problem, which is related, among other things, to the delayed occurrence of effects, the literature – but also politics – refer to the "measurability problem" (e.g. Bühner et al. 2022). For the monitoring of effects, operationalisation in the form of criteria and indicators is necessary. The development of indicators is accompanied by the challenge that non-physical variables in particular, such as social constructs (e.g. learning processes or trust-building), are difficult to measure. When selecting indicators, both the existing methodological know-how and the available resources (e.g. human and financial) should be taken into account so that the effort required for collection remains within reasonable limits. It is usually advisable to define a mix of qualitative and quantitative indicators, as this allows different types of effects to be traced (Bühner et al. 2022). Descriptions based exclusively on pre-developed indicators also carry the risk that not all impact-relevant process developments (e.g. unintended side effects) are captured. Similarly, indicators should be considered along the entire impact chain and not only at the outcome level.

When using the criteria and exemplary indicators of the orientation guide developed here to strengthen impact orientation and measurement,

the risk of confirmation bias must be taken into account. It is important to critically reflect on the extent to which studies aligned with the guide for assessment seek to confirm the impact categories outlined therein.

This risk exists in all research frameworks that are provided for support. One possible approach to counter this is to integrate heterogeneous perspectives in the sense of a co-evaluation (van Drooge & Spaapen 2022). Furthermore, the boundaries between the impact categories are not clearly defined, which is not necessary for a heuristic such as this.

Transdisciplinary impact descriptions and co-evaluations go hand in hand with the challenge of positionality among project participants. This leads to a diversity of perspectives, also with regard to the effects that are (or can be) achieved through transdisciplinary and participatory research. Ideally, the different perspectives of the cooperating actors on the processes, results and impacts should be integrated with their respective foci and attributions of meaning. In reality, however, it is clear that this requirement cannot always be met. For this reason, creating transparency is an important task that transdisciplinary teams should work on together.

PART II EXAMPLES OF APPLICATION OF THE ORIENTATION GUIDE

After presenting the orientation guide with criteria and indicators for describing and recording impacts in Part I, Part II uses three examples to illustrate how it can be applied. Examples were deliberately selected from different fields of transdisciplinary and participatory research: from citizen science research, participatory health research (using the example of psychiatry-related research) and transdisciplinary research in the field of sustainable urban development⁵. The application examples differ in the type, intensity and objectives of the participation of non-scientific actors.

The examples are all projects that are still ongoing or have already been completed. What the completed projects have in common is that they were only recently completed, so that at this point in time it is only possible to make limited statements about effects that occurred after the end of the project. Furthermore, none of the projects included a subproject or separate work package that explicitly addressed the monitoring and evaluation. The authors were therefore only able to draw on empirical data to a limited extent in their impact reflection.

The texts first describe the context (participants, funding, duration), the projects' objectives and the methodology used. The authors then select the criteria and indicators that are relevant to the respective research context and reflect on some of the achieved effects. The chapters conclude with a reflection on the application of the guide for assessment.

The authors have used the orientation guide in different ways. The tests show that it is suitable for the following:

- raising awareness of the specific features of the design and management of TDPR on the basis of the criteria and indicators for process quality and integrating these as requirements into the respective project.
- to gain an impression of possible criteria and indicators for impact assessment, e.g. for planning monitoring at the start of a research project or for evaluation during or after completion of the project. In the citizen science projects presented as examples, the orientation guide is used to gain a clearer understanding of the suitability of criteria and indicators in projects with varying degrees of participation intensity. This reflection took place in consultation with those responsible for project implementation. This subchapter does not provide an assessment of the effects achieved.
- to select criteria and indicators that appear appropriate for the respective project objectives and forms of participation and – depending on the availability of empirical data – to reflect in more or less detail on the outcomes and impacts that have been achieved or can still be expected. The application examples served as "finger exercises" – in real research contexts, it is advisable to use monitoring data for impact assessment and to carry out the evaluation in a larger group of project participants (co-evaluation).

All authors pointed out the challenge of estimating and attributing longer-term impacts, as it is often precisely these more far-reaching objectives and societal changes that motivate non-scientific actors in particular to participate. However, as outlined in Chapter 4 of the guide, these are fundamental methodological problems associated with tracking complex impact chains.

⁵ The examples of application were written by researchers who were involved in the projects presented (Sebastian von Peter and Franziska Ehnert). Olivia Höhener wrote the two examples from citizen science research in her role as managing director of the Citizen Science Zurich competence centre and reviewed the statements with academic researchers and citizen scientists from both projects. All three authors have academic backgrounds.

1. APPLICATION EXAMPLES FROM THE FIELD OF CITIZEN SCIENCE

Olivia Höhener in collaboration with Sandra Gloor, Anouk-Lisa Taucher, Kevin Vega, Yvonne Ilg, Anke Maatz and Henrike Wiemer

Citizen science projects cover a wide range of participation forms. The citizen science research community therefore broadly distinguishes between three different types of projects: contributory, collaborative and co-created projects (see Figure 1).

While citizens usually participate in data collection and/or processing in "contributory" projects, they are already involved in developing the research question in co-created projects. Furthermore, in some co-created projects, citizens are part of the project management team and have the same decision-making power as academic researchers throughout the entire project. This fundamental difference between the types of projects is also reflected in the desired outcomes: while in contri-

butory projects, citizens *contribute* to generating scientific knowledge and answering a question that has been defined by academic researchers, co-created projects aim to understand and improve the everyday lives of the citizens involved and *empower* them to represent their interests independently and autonomously. They are guided by the living environments and challenges of the groups involved and require a different type of participation and process design to ensure that the collaboration is successful and the intended effects are achieved. Depending on the type and design of a project, the dimensions and criteria listed in the orientation guide are therefore relevant to varying degrees and can be described by different indicators.

Figure 1: Three types of citizen science projects.
© Citizen Science Zurich; Ursina Rofler

To illustrate these differences and provide guidance to project managers, two project examples will be used: the project "Swallowtail & Silk bees -

pollen-gathering insects in the city of Zurich" as a contributory project and the project "Let's talk about it! But how?" as a co-created project.

1.1 Context of the Example Projects

1.1.1 Project "Swallowtails & Silk Bees - Pollen-gathering Insects in the City of Zurich"

Project partners:

Department of Environmental Systems Science, ETH Zurich and Projekt StadtWildTiere Schweiz

Duration: Oct. 2021 – Dec. 2023

Web: Swallowtail & Silk Bees – pollen-gathering insects in the City of Zurich

Background

Pollinating insects play a crucial role, as approximately 80% of wild and cultivated plants depend on pollination. However, the last half-century has seen a dramatic decline in insect populations, which is part of an accelerating biodiversity crisis. According to the Red List, around half of all bee and butterfly species in Switzerland are endangered. This decline is particularly noticeable in cities, where pollen shortages and habitat fragmentation threaten urban biodiversity. However, with the right planning and management, cities can be a refuge for pollinators.

Objectives

The project aimed to raise awareness among the urban population of the ecology and importance of the mutual relationships between plants and pollinators on their doorsteps and to highlight the potential of their local green spaces as part of a larger urban network and ecosystem. The aim was to change and expand people's perception of cities as complex ecosystems and their responsibility for their maintenance. Research results from previous projects were to be used and expanded to examine whether greater plant diversity also leads to a higher number and diversity of pollinators.

Involvement of citizen scientists

A pollinator survey was conducted in the city of Zurich with the help of volunteers. The volunteers were trained to identify a selection of insect pollinators, with a focus on wild bees and butterflies. They then went to urban green spaces (along green tram tracks, on tree grates and in large wildflower meadows) to identify and record the flower visitors in their chosen area. During the summer months, they returned regularly to their study areas and observed how the flower visitors changed over the seasons and with the maintenance of the green space. This data was used to investigate how the size of green spaces, their connectivity and flower diversity affect pollinator biodiversity.

Financial support

Else v. Sick Foundation, Erica Foundation, Ernst Göhner Foundation, Gust and Lyn Guhl Foundation, Hand in Hand Anstalt, Grün Stadt Zürich, Pancivis Foundation, Citizen Science Zurich (Seed Grant), EXEKIAS Foundation, Temperatio Foundation, Uranus Foundation, Vontobel Foundation, SWILD Research and Consulting Community, and other foundations that wish to remain anonymous.

1.1.2 Context of the Project "Let's talk about it! But how?"

Project partners

German Department, University of Zurich, Psychiatric University Hospital Zurich

Duration: since August 2020

Web: <https://drueberreden.ch/>

Background

Talking about mental illness can help people cope with their condition. However, social taboos, stigmatisation, feelings of grief and shame, and the unfamiliarity of the experience often make talking about mental illness difficult.

Objectives

From a linguistic, psychiatric and experiential perspective, the project investigates how talking about mental health and illness can nevertheless be successful. What strategies help when talking to family, employers or friends? How can the experience of mental illness be put into words and shared?

The project aims to bring the findings into professional practice and the public sphere in order to contribute to a more understanding and open dialogue about mental illness. In addition to identifying theoretical findings, the project also aims to

give those affected and their families a greater voice.

Involvement of citizen scientists

In order to identify helpful strategies for talking about mental illness, conversations about mental illness are recorded in different contexts and, using interdisciplinary, predominantly qualitative methods (content and conversation analysis), communicative solutions are sought for the difficult task of verbalising mental experiences. The participation of all (those affected, relatives, employers, professionals) in project planning, data acquisition and analysis, and communication of results is a core element of the project.

Financial support

Guido Fluri Foundation, Foundation for the Promotion of Psychiatry and Psychotherapy, Citizen Science Zurich (seed grant) and Hans and Marianne Schwyn Foundation.

1.2 Exemplary Operationalisation of the Guide

Dimension: Process Quality

CRITERIA	INDICATORS – SWALLOWTAIL & SILK BEES	INDICATORS – LET'S TALK ABOUT IT
Power to act		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Was decision-making power shared? → Were bottom-up processes (in the sense of contributing ideas) possible?
Inclusivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Was attention paid to the diversity of the participants' backgrounds in terms of life experience and knowledge (e.g. gender, age, socio-economic background, etc.)? → Was the work carried out in a language that was accessible to everyone? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were representatives of all relevant stakeholder groups able to participate/contribute? → Was the work carried out in a language that was accessible to everyone?
Integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Are the issues addressed of interest or relevance to all participants? → Were (all) actors from the relevant fields of action involved at an early stage? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Are the issues addressed of interest or relevance to all participants? → Were all relevant forms of knowledge (research and practice) included? → Were (all) actors from the relevant fields of action involved at an early stage?
Transparency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were roles and expertise clearly defined/communicated? → Were expectations communicated (on an ongoing basis)? → Were contact persons and responsibilities clear to everyone? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were roles and expertise clearly defined/communicated? → Were expectations communicated (on an ongoing basis)? → Were contact persons and responsibilities clear to everyone? → Were the objectives and interests of the individual participants in the project clearly stated? → Were decision-making criteria and processes clearly outlined? → Were the methods used in the project clearly communicated to promote the traceability of results and confidence in them?

Dimension: Process Quality

CRITERIA	INDICATORS – SWALLOWTAIL & SILK BEES	INDICATORS – LET'S TALK ABOUT IT
Communication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were there defined channels for two-way communication with/ from the project management? → Were communication channels or media provided for exchange among project participants? → Did all project participants have access to knowledge relevant to the project and to the insights generated by the project? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were there defined channels for two-way communication with/ from the project management? → Were communication channels or media provided for exchange among project participants? → Were the communication channels accessible to everyone without barriers? → Did all project participants have access to knowledge relevant to the project and to the insights generated by the project?
Definition of objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were non-academic objectives also taken into account? → Was the research project aligned with the needs and expectations of the future users of the results? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were non-academic goals also taken into account? → Were the intended effects reflected by practitioners at an early stage? → Was the research project aligned with the needs and expectations of the future users of the results?
Adaptability /iterativity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Was there sufficient room for feedback/exchange/ comments? → Were uncertainties in the knowledge base and complex interrelationships taken into account during the course of the project? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Was the research process open/flexible enough to allow for co-determination? → Was there sufficient room for feedback/exchange/comments? → Did the project offer opportunities for different forms of learning? → In addition, were the opportunities for participation flexible (in terms of the type of participation and the duration of participation)?

Dimension: Process Quality

CRITERIA	INDICATORS – SWALLOWTAIL & SILK BEE	INDICATORS – LET'S TALK ABOUT IT
Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Was the process experienced as appreciative by all participants? → Did the process enable the development of mutual trust and understanding? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were power imbalances, differences in knowledge and experience between those involved reflected upon? → Was the process experienced as appreciative by all participants? → Did the process enable the development of mutual trust and understanding? → Were different time logics taken into account? → Was there an attitude that allowed for learning from mistakes? → Were structurally determined inequalities in opportunities and resources reflected upon or compensated for?
Clarification of outputs/outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were different outputs promoted for different target groups? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Did the project benefit all participants and were these benefits reasonably balanced? → Were different outputs promoted for different target groups? → In addition, was there sufficient room for negotiating the desired outputs? → Was there sufficient space for negotiating authorship and questions of ownership?
Dissemination of results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were the requirements of the target groups taken into account in the type of outputs? → Was the dissemination of results actively promoted? (e.g. presentations, references in newsletters, social media)? 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were the requirements of the target groups taken into account in the type of outputs? → Was there cooperation with representatives of the target group (e.g. multipliers) to disseminate the results? → Was the dissemination of results actively promoted? (e.g. presentations, references in newsletters, social media, publications)? → Were results made permanently freely accessible? (open access etc.)

Dimension: Outcome – Sphere of Control

CRITERIA	INDICATORS – SWALLOWTAIL & SILK BEE	INDICATORS – LET’S TALK ABOUT IT
<p>Promotion of learning processes (cognitive, normative)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System knowledge (analytical): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Expansion of knowledge about characteristics, dynamics and cause-and-effect relationships in <i>socio-ecological</i> systems ▪ Development of a common problem understanding • Target knowledge (normative): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Shared understanding of guiding principles and visions for the future ▪ Change in attitudes, values and preferences • Transformation knowledge (actionable knowledge): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Capacity building: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promotion of scientific literacy/understanding of scientific processes - Practical skills (in this case, species identification) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognition and integration of plural forms of knowledge, such as everyday and experiential knowledge, marginalised perspectives/knowledge • System knowledge (analytical): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Expansion of knowledge about characteristics, dynamics and cause-and-effect relationships in socio-institutional systems ▪ Development of a common problem understanding • Target knowledge (normative): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Shared understanding of guiding principles and visions for the future ▪ Change in attitudes, values, and preferences ▪ Change in role understanding • Transformation knowledge (actionable knowledge): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mutual learning: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Mutual learning about the perspectives, rationales - Development of a common understanding of options for action in the respective field of research ▪ Capacity building: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - E .g. skills for reflection and co-creation of knowledge, learning TDPR methods - Promotion of scientific literacy/understanding of scientific processes - Empathy and conflict mediation skills - Practical skills (e.g. taking and analysing water samples, repairing, processing local fruit varieties)

Dimension: Outcome – Sphere of Control

CRITERIA	INDICATORS – SWALLOWTAIL & SILK BEE	INDICATORS – LET'S TALK ABOUT IT
Strengthening social relationships and cooperation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network building • Community building and development of collective identities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network building • Building trust and mutual understanding, including for differences • Community building and development of collective identities • Development of strategic contacts
Strengthening reputation		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening individual reputation
Emotional changes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Changes in motivation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experience of self-efficacy (e.g. change in self-image and self-esteem) • Change in motivation
Strengthening empowerment		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expansion of resources and capacities to act (e.g. financial resources, space) • Being heard and recognised with one's own perspectives and positions • Strengthening one's own power to act through networking with like-minded people
Changes in actions and practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiences with disrupting routines and trying out new practices in various fields of action (e.g. on private green spaces/balconies) • Changes in organisational practices (e.g. municipal services) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiences with disrupting routines and trying out new practices in various fields of action (e.g. through conducting conversation and treatment) • Changes in organisational practices
Institutional changes		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Temporary) institutional changes (e.g. new positions, areas of responsibilities) • Changes in governance (e.g. more participation and co-creation, changes in regulations)
Infrastructural changes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Temporary) changes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Built infrastructure (e.g. settlement structures and buildings, road space) ▪ Green and blue infrastructure (e.g. green spaces, water) 	

Dimension: Impact – Sphere of Influence

CRITERIA	INDICATORS – SWALLOWTAIL & SILK BEE	INDICATORS – LET'S TALK ABOUT IT
Stabilisation and expansion of activities & practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the project context: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Follow-up projects (using own resources or via funding bodies) • Transfer to other temporal and spatial contexts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Follow-up projects in other contexts 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In the project context: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Follow-up projects (using own resources or via funding bodies) • Transfer to other temporal and spatial contexts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Follow-up projects in other contexts ▪ Implementation of project results in other contexts ▪ Extension of modified practices to other stakeholder groups
Expansion and deepening of cooperation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of new (strategic) contacts and partnerships (e.g. with intermediaries and multipliers, decision-makers at various levels and in various institutional contexts) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of new (strategic) contacts and partnerships (e.g. with intermediaries and multipliers, decision-makers at various levels and in various institutional contexts) • Establishment of new networks and communities of practice (e.g. practice-research networks) • Institutionalisation and professionalisation of networks
Knowledge transfer and acquisition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge transfer beyond the project context to other temporal and spatial contexts (e.g. through the involvement of intermediaries and multipliers, target group-oriented events and publications) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Knowledge transfer beyond the project context to other temporal and spatial contexts (e.g. through the involvement of intermediaries and multipliers, target group-oriented events and publications)

Dimension: Impact – Sphere of Influence

CRITERIA	INDICATORS – SWALLOWTAIL & SILK BEE	INDICATORS – LET'S TALK ABOUT IT
Change in knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishment of new/changed paradigms and concepts (e.g. sustainable urban development) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishment of new/changed paradigms and concepts (e.g. new understandings of "illness and health") Recognition and integration of plural forms of knowledge (see outcome) Integration of knowledge into practices, research, teaching, and practical infrastructures, institutions and discourses Changed training content
Establishment of new/changed practices and routines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> E.g. in construction, urban planning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> E.g. in health maintenance and care
Establishment of new/changed discourses and narratives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Changed perception of one's own environment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishment of new/changed world views, values, and concepts (e.g. paradigm shifts, understanding of health and prevention, role of science in society)
Establishment of new/changed institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishment of a new institution within the authority to promote biodiversity and ecological green space planning Establishment of institutions to continue project activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishment of new/changed forms of decision-making and governance in research and practice (e.g. participatory and co-creative decision-making, more decentralised and power-sensitive cooperation) Establishment of new/changed role profiles and forms of expertise (e.g. positions, facilitators, knowledge brokers, change in the understanding of the role of scientific institutions) Establishment of a new/changed management and collaboration culture in organisations (removal of barriers and improvement of accessibility)

Dimension: Impact – Sphere of Influence

CRITERIA	INDICATORS – SWALLOWTAIL & SILK BEE	INDICATORS – LET’S TALK ABOUT IT
Establishment of new/changed infrastructures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Green and blue infrastructure (e.g. green spaces, water) • Removal of barriers and increased accessibility (for wildlife) 	
Transformation of power relations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening of participation and social inclusion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening of participation and social inclusion • Changed distribution of decision-making authority and power to act (e.g. participatory decision-making structures) • Changed distribution of resources (e.g. finances, financial support for practice partners) within the project
Economic effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Securing livelihoods, i.e. satisfying basic needs – in the project context, this primarily benefits wildlife, but humans also benefit 	
Ecological effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preservation or enhancement of biodiversity • Strengthening ecosystem services: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Provisioning services 	
Societal effects		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improving the quality of life and opportunities, especially for socially disadvantaged groups (e.g. health, well-being and self-care)

1.3 Reflection on the Application of the Guide for Assessment

With its indicative list of possible effects, the guide for assessment provides useful support for citizen science projects regardless of their degree of participation. It can be used for project planning as well as for reflection during the course of the project or after its completion.

In project planning, it can serve as a starting point, particularly in the dimension "process quality", for considering criteria that can positively influence the cooperation of all participants and thus the course of the project and the achievement of its impact. At the same time, in the dimension "outcome", it points to important aspects and groups of people

beyond the citizens involved (e.g. multipliers, representatives from politics and administration) who should also be considered at an early stage and actively involved in order to achieve the desired impact.

However, within citizen science projects, there may be different degrees of participation for different groups of people: while an expert with practical experience has "equal" decision-making power as part of the project management team, other citizens may "only" contribute to data collection or analysis during the course of the project. In this case, no decision-making power is shared with them, but depending on the project, they may contribute ideas that can be taken into account during the course of the project.

When selecting suitable or relevant indicators, it is therefore important to bear in mind that these may only be relevant for some of those involved in the project. Given that not all those involved in citizen science wish to take on responsibility and that some prefer to make a selective contribution, it makes sense to differentiate in this regard from the perspective of the citizens involved. The same applies to indicators such as capacity building: this might not be necessary to the same extent for everyone but depends on the degree of involvement of the participants.

In the case of an interim evaluation or an evaluation after project completion, the guide is helpful in critically reflecting on the various dimensions of impact. It quickly becomes clear that although many indicators are considered important for the project (possibly because they are similar within a criterion), it is usually not realistic to actually collect data for all relevant indicators within the scope of an evaluation due to resource constraints. The wealth and diversity of indicators is helpful for an ongoing (self-)critical reflection on cooperation during the course of the project, but for conducting an evaluation the selection must be narrowed down considerably.

Although measuring impact is difficult due to its dependence on larger contexts and time frames, the guide for assessment is nevertheless helpful in distinguishing more clearly between the effects directly associated with a project (outcome) and those that can only be influenced or to which only a contribution can be made (impact).

The two project examples presented clearly show that in co-created projects, the quality of the processes, in particular cooperation on an equal footing and trust-building, makes a much greater contribution to achieving impact than is the case in contributory projects. In the latter, aspects such as clear, transparent communication and correspondingly low-threshold, attractive communication channels predominate. Highlighting this fact is helpful in itself.

• 2. APPLICATION EXAMPLE FROM PARTICIPATORY HEALTH RESEARCH

Sebastian von Peter

2.1 Context of the ImpPeer-Psy5 Project: Peer Support in Psychiatric Care – Implementation Conditions in the Care Sector Under Social Code Book V

Background

For more than 30 years, people with personal experience of mental health crises have been contributing to psychosocial and psychiatric healthcare as recovery or peer support workers (=PSW*). At the same time, numerous publications discuss the challenges of implementing PSW in psychiatric and other care contexts. The question of its implementation in the health insurance-financed sector has come to the fore in Germany due to a new personnel regulation adopted in 2016. Core tasks for this new professional group must be defined and remuneration regulations established.

Objectives

In this context, the ImpPeer-Psy5 study aimed firstly to assess the current status of PSW implementation in health insurance-funded psychiatric care in Germany. Secondly, the different needs of the stakeholder groups involved in this implementation (PSW*, other employees (=EM) and users of care services (=US)) were identified in order to derive concrete strategies from the current situation and needs.

Method

The study was funded by the Innovation Fund of the Joint Federal Committee (=GBA) from 2020 to 2023. It used a mixed-method QUAL-QUAN-QUAL design to derive implementation strategies based on different methodological approaches and the collection of diverging perspectives. Two qualitative research phases (QUAL1 and QUAL2) flanked a standardised survey (QUAN) to examine the status and needs of PSWs in psychiatric care throughout Germany, supplemented by a systematic review on the topic and a series of theory-of-change workshops to develop strategies for successful implementation.

Consortium

The research consortium consisted of three sub-teams: one team at the Brandenburg Medical School (MHB), which carried out both QUAL parts; one team at the University Medical Centre Hamburg-Eppendorf, which was responsible for the other parts of the study; and one team at the non-profit training provider for PSW* EX-IN Germany, which acted as a practice partner. In addition, the study used a collaborative research approach in combination with participatory methods and strategies to involve various interest groups in different phases of the research process. In this context, collaborative means cooperation between researchers with and without personal experience of mental health crises and experience of using psychiatric services in all phases of the study: in developing the proposal and research questions, during the collection, analysis and interpretation of data, and during the publication of the results. All team members were employed as research assistants and had different professional, academic and experiential backgrounds. In addition to this collaborative research approach, participatory work-shops were carried out in various stages of the study and research phases to involve a wide range of actors with experience in the implementation of PSW in Germany, such as: PSW* working within or outside the health care system, US of psychiatric care services, persons involved in political self-advocacy, and US of self-help groups. It is also crucial to mention that the EM members of the research teams came from different disciplines. They had scientific qualifications in health research, medicine, anthropology, gender studies, nursing, cultural studies, linguistics and literary studies, religious studies, philosophy, history, art history and psychology, which made the ImpPeer-Psy5 study a highly interdisciplinary project.

Outputs: The main output were 40 recommendations for implementing PSW, which were developed on the basis of the triangulated results of all parts of the study in ongoing collaborative workshops. These overarching recommendations were discussed with regard to the current implementation situation of PSW and upcoming health policy decisions. This led to concrete recommendations and procedures for the future implementation of PSW, which were summarised in a final report to the GBA.

In addition to scientific publications of the results of the various parts of the study (results of the systematic review, the theory of change, the qualitative surveys and the standardised questionnaire), the recommendations and results were also prepared for a non-academic readership – for political decision-makers, practitioners from various professional groups, PSW* and US – and distributed to these groups. In addition to this result report, the following three strategies were used:

- Dynamic cartography for monitoring PSW implementation: nationwide preparation of the status of PSW implementation in the form of an accessible visualisation.
- Closing events to publish and discuss key findings: To disseminate the main results to

a wider audience, three online events were held, dealing with scientific issues (event 1), health policy concerns (event 2) and everyday/practice-oriented discussions (event 3) on the implementation of PSWs. National and international representatives from politics, academia and practice were invited to comment on the study results, and invitations to the event were widely distributed via various distribution lists for psychiatric policy and care as well as self-help and self-advocacy groups. The events were recorded and are now freely available online (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s3020OXN0EM&t=3693s>).

- Understandable summary of the key findings in a brochure: Recommendations that facilitate BGB implementation and are therefore made available to the general public (https://www.mhb-fontane.de/files/Dateien/Forschungsiags/250801_ImpPeer_Doppelseiten_final.pdf).

Finally, in the QUAL sub-project, the benefits of collaborative work were first reflected within the MHB team and then evaluated with the help of three focus groups (<https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC12070662/>).

2.2 Exemplary Operationalisation of the Guide

This reflection refers to the QUAL study parts because these were located at the reporting institution, the Medical School Brandenburg (=MHB).

Dimension: Process Quality

CRITERIA	INDICATORS	APPLICATION IMPPEER-PSY5
Power to act	→ Has the power to act been (re)distributed?	Important for collaborative work
	→ Was decision-making power shared?	Reflection on the topic of collaboration see in the publication (link on the p.36)
	→ Were bottom-up processes possible?	
Inclusivity	→ Were the necessary measures taken to ensure accessibility?	
	→ Were representatives of all relevant stakeholder groups able to participate/contribute?	
	→ Was attention paid to the diversity of the participants' backgrounds in terms of life experience and knowledge (e.g. gender, age, socio-economic background, etc.)?	
	→ Was the work carried out in a language that was accessible to everyone?	
Integration	→ Are the issues addressed of interest or relevance to all participants?	The teams were set up collaboratively and the application was formulated collaboratively.
	→ Were all relevant forms of knowledge (research and practice) included?	Cross-study questions were discussed and agreed upon with participants from diverse knowledge and professional backgrounds.
	→ Were the different perspectives/forms of knowledge linked in order to develop system-oriented solutions?	
	→ Were (all) actors from the relevant fields of action involved at an early stage?	The final events aimed at different target groups.

Dimension: Process Quality

CRITERIA	INDICATORS	APPLICATION IMPPEER-PSY5
Transparency	→ Was (limited) scope for action (e.g. due to the type of funding allocation) communicated?	Extensive discussion of the limitations of the scope for action within the framework of the publication on the methodological approach.
	→ Were roles and expertise clearly defined/communicated?	
	→ Were expectations communicated (on an ongoing basis)?	Ongoing negotiation of roles and expertise within the project.
	→ Were contact persons and responsibilities clear to everyone?	
	→ Were the objectives of the project and the interests of the individual participants clearly stated?	
	→ Were decision-making criteria and processes clearly outlined?	Exchange of expectations and positions in ongoing supervision meetings. Unclear whether the project goals were clear to everyone during the participatory workshops and final events. Detailed presentation of the methods in a publication and in a way that is understandable to laypeople during the first final event/in the brochure (see link above, p.36).
	→ Were the methods used in the project clearly communicated to promote the traceability of the results and confidence in them?	
→ Were uncertainties in the level of knowledge and complex interrelationships openly explained during the course of the project?		
Communication	→ Were there defined channels for two-way communication with/ from the project management?	Communication between the participating students was also difficult due to the physical distances involved.
	→ Were communication channels or media provided for exchange among project participants?	
	→ Were the communication channels accessible to everyone without barriers?	Lead time for sending out materials for the participatory workshops and final events may not have been sufficient.
	→ Was planning done in advance so that all participants could be involved with sufficient notice and receive feedback on their contributions?	
	→ Did all project participants have access to knowledge relevant to the project and to the insights generated by the project?	

Dimension: Process Quality

CRITERIA	INDICATORS	APPLICATION IMPPEER-PSY5
Definition of objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were differing definitions of objectives possible/were conflicting objectives made visible? → Were non-academic objectives also taken into account? → Were the intended effects aimed for the practitioners reflected on at an early stage? → Were possible negative effects and risks reflected on at an early stage? → Was the research project aligned with the needs and expectations of the future users of the results? 	<p>Repeated negotiation of conflicting goals in the overall and MHB sub-teams.</p> <p>Attempt to take non-scientific objectives into account by producing a brochure and dynamic cartography.</p> <p>Reflection on possible effects, especially at the level of the research teams and in the context of the final events.</p>
Adaptability/iterativity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Was the research process open/flexible enough to allow for co-determination? → Were those involved sufficiently open to change? → Was there sufficient room for feedback/exchange/comments? → Were there opportunities to document and reflect on unexpected developments? → Were uncertainties in the knowledge base and complex interrelationships taken into account during the course of the project? → Did the project offer opportunities for different forms of learning? 	<p>Strong restrictions on the co-determination of members of the research team and participants through the design, the research focus, and the specification of methods – reflection in the context of the publication of methods.</p> <p>Far too little time/space for feedback within the MHB sub-team, the various teams of the consortium and for even more participatory cooperation.</p> <p>A lot, but not enough opportunity for mutual learning (e.g. on positions towards PSW and psychiatry).</p>

Dimension: Process Quality

CRITERIA	INDICATORS	APPLICATION IMPPEER-PSYS
Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were power imbalances between the participants reflected upon? → Was the process experienced as appreciative by all participants ? → Were emotions allowed during the collaboration? Were they tolerated? → Did the process enable the development of mutual trust and understanding ? → Were different time logics taken into account? → Was there an attitude that allowed for learning from mistakes? → Were structurally determined inequalities in opportunities and resources reflected upon or compensated for? 	<p>Various supervision formats, which were nevertheless insufficient to reflect the imbalances at various levels.</p> <p>Emotional interactions in the project work of the MHB sub-team that pushed people to their limits. Understanding and comprehension improved compared to the start of the project; could have been further developed with sufficient time.</p> <p>Culture that enables mutual criticism varied greatly depending on the topic and those involved; thematically, there was a lot at stake.</p>
Clarification of outputs/ outcomes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Did the project benefit all participants and were these benefits reasonably balanced? → Were different outputs promoted – for different target groups? → Was there sufficient space for negotiating authorship and questions of ownership? 	<p>Evaluation of the output that is useful for all parties is pending.</p> <p>There was output for different target groups; however, the formats could have been more diverse.</p> <p>Negotiation of authorship is still ongoing; overall, authorship is more balance compared to previous collaborative projects.</p>

Dimension: Process Quality

CRITERIA	INDICATORS	APPLICATION IMPPEER-PSYS
Dissemination of results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were the requirements of the target groups taken into account in the type of outputs? (Target group-appropriate language, formats, scope, relevance to action) → Was there collaboration with representatives of the target group (e.g. multipliers) to disseminate results? → Was the dissemination of results actively promoted? (e.g. presentations, references in newsletters, social media) → Were results made permanently freely accessible? (open access, etc.) 	<p>Output formats that are understandable to laypeople were made possible by reallocating project funds.</p> <p>Currently dissemination with the help of multipliers; an evaluation of the impact/outcomes would be useful.</p>

Dimension: Outcome

CRITERIA	EXEMPLARY INDICATORS	APPLICATION	IMPEER-PSY5
Promotion of learning processes (cognitive, normative)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Recognition and integration of plural forms of knowledge, such as everyday and experiential knowledge, indigenous knowledge, marginalised perspectives/ knowledge bases 	<p>The diversity of the research team's knowledge and experience was a recurring theme during the work of the MHB sub-team.</p>	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System knowledge (analytical): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Expansion of knowledge about characteristics, dynamics, and cause-and-effect relationships in socio-ecological, socio-technical and socio-institutional systems ▪ Development of a common understanding of the problem 	<p>Intensive examination of the conditions of psychiatric care as an implementation context for PSW.</p>	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target knowledge (normative) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Shared understanding of guiding principles and visions for the future ▪ Change in attitudes, values and preferences ▪ Change in role understanding (individual and organisational) 	<p>Target knowledge: Collaborative agreement on cross-study recommendations during the final phase of the project</p>	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transformation knowledge (actionable knowledge): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mutual learning: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Mutual learning about perspectives, logic of action and needs of others – Development of a common understanding of options for action in the respective field of research 	<p>Extensive discussion of differing perspectives/positions within the collaborative research team in almost every session.</p>	

Dimension: Outcome

CRITERIA	EXEMPLARY INDICATORS	APPLICATION	IMPEER-PSY5
Promotion of learning processes (cognitive, normative)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Capacity building: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – E.g. skills for reflection co-creation of knowledge, learning TDPR methods – Promotion of scientific literacy/ understanding of scientific processes – Empathy and conflict mediation skills – Practical skills (e.g. public relations, taking and analysing water samples, repairing, processing local fruit varieties) 	Mutual capacity building through co-creation of knowledge, (bilateral) promotion of understanding of scientific processes through work on improving cooperation skills.	
Strengthening of social relationships and cooperation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Network building • Building trust and mutual understanding, including for differences • Community building and development of collective identities • Development of strategic contacts 	<p>Networking with national (and in some cases international) PSW actors.</p> <p>Working on trust and understanding within the sub-teams.</p>	
Strengthening reputation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening individual reputations • Strengthening organisational reputation 	Strengthening the individual and organisational reputation of PSW and PSW*	
Emotional changes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experience of self-efficacy (e.g. change in self-image and self-esteem) • Change in motivation 	Change in the self-image of the researchers involved.	

Dimension: Outcome

CRITERIA	EXEMPLARY INDICATORS	APPLICATION	IMPEER-PSYS
Strengthening empowerment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expanding resources and capacities to act (e.g. financial resources, space) • Being heard and recognised with one's own perspectives and positions • Strengthening one's own power to act through collaboration and networking with "like-minded people" (e.g. citizens in citizen science, cooperation between patients) 	Difficult to assess for all participating researchers and other stakeholders; evaluation would be necessary.	
Changes in actions and practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experiences with disrupting routines and trying out new practices in various fields of action (e.g. mobility, nutrition, health care and treatment) • Changes in organisational practices 	The project aimed to change practices; this would be needed to be evaluated in a follow-up implementation study.	
Institutional changes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Temporary) institutional changes (e.g. new positions, areas of responsibilities) • Changes in governance (e.g. more participation and co-creation, changes in regulations) 	See above. Evaluation in a follow-up study is necessary. The study aimed to develop implementation recommendations for a new occupational group – will the results be incorporated into the future regulations on staff in psychiatric care?	
Infrastructural changes		Not applicable due to the thematic focus area.	

Dimension: Impact

The impact criteria were difficult to assess. On the one hand, this was because the guide for assessment was applied relatively shortly after the project was completed, but on the other hand, it was also because, as expected, it is generally difficult to attribute further effects to specific causes.

CRITERIA	EXEMPLARY INDICATORS	APPLICATION	IMPEER-PSYS
Continuation and expansion of activities & practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In the project context: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Follow-up projects (from own resources or via funding bodies) Transfer to other temporal and spatial contexts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Follow-up projects in other contexts Implementation of project results in other contexts Extension of changed practices to other stakeholder groups 	<p>This is a useful criterion.</p> <p>A follow-up study would be necessary to examine changes in action/implementation practices.</p>	
Expansion and deepening of cooperation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Establishment of new (strategic) contacts and partnerships (e.g. with intermediaries and multipliers, decision-makers at various levels and in various institutional contexts) Establishment of new networks and communities of practice (e.g. practice-research networks) Institutionalisation and professionalisation of networks 	<p>As part of the project, all nationwide providers of PSW trainings have networked (to implement dynamic cartography and explore synergies in relation to health policy work).</p> <p>– This may also count as an outcome and an impact because it facilitates future projects.</p>	
Knowledge transfer and absorption	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Knowledge transfer beyond the project context to other temporal and spatial contexts (e.g. through the involvement of intermediaries and multipliers, target group-oriented events and publications) 	<p>A follow-up survey or follow-up project would be necessary to evaluate the impact of the final events and the brochure/scientific publications.</p>	

Dimension: Impact

CRITERIA	EXEMPLARY INDICATORS	APPLICATION IMPEER-PSYS
Change in knowledge bases	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of new/changed paradigms and concepts (e.g. sustainable urban development, regenerative agriculture, new understanding of "illness and health") • Recognition and integration of plural forms of knowledge (see outcome) • Integration of knowledge into practices, research, teaching and practice infrastructures, institutions, and discourses • Changed training content 	<p>Various publications attempt to (not yet common in Germany) promote a critical understanding of PSW. It is not yet clear to what extent this has been successful and whether this knowledge is finding its way into different knowledge and work contexts.</p>
Establishment of new/changed practices and routines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of e.g. health maintenance, care, nutrition, mobility, consumption, energy production, construction, urban planning 	<p>A useful indicator for a follow-up project: can only be clarified through a follow-up study focusing on implementation.</p>
Establishing new/changed discourses and narratives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of new/changed world views, values, and concepts (e.g. paradigm shifts, understanding of health and prevention, role of science in society) 	<p>These changes could be tracked within the research team and also addressed in the publications; effects beyond this are difficult to determine.</p>
Establishment of new/changed institutional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of new/changed forms of decision-making and governance in research and practice (e.g. participatory and co-creative decision-making, more decentralised and power-sensitive cooperation) • Establishment of new/changed regulations and laws • Establishment of new/changed organisational units (e.g. sustainability department, prevention department) • Establishment of new/changed role profiles and forms of expertise (e.g. positions, facilitators, knowledge brokers, change in the understanding of the role of science as an institution) 	<p>Impact of the brochure on the topic of impacts still unclear.</p> <p>Possible contribution to further effects: Impact on the adaptation of staff regulations and on future implementation practices of the PSW</p>

Dimension: Impact

CRITERIA	EXEMPLARY INDICATORS	APPLICATION	IMPEER-PSYS
Establishment of new/changed institutional	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of a new/changed management and collaboration culture in organisations (removal of barriers or improvement of accessibility) • Establishment of institutions to continue project activities (e.g. establishment of real-world laboratories and/or funding guidelines and programmes, support for collaborative working groups) 	See previous page	
Establishment of new/changed infrastructures		Not applicable due to the subject area	
Transformation of power relations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthening participation and social inclusion • Changed distribution of decision-making authority and power to act (e.g. participatory decision-making structures) • Changed distribution of resources (e.g. finances, financial support for practice partners) • Changed access to and distribution of knowledge and skills (e.g. open access, public libraries) 	Possible contribution to further effects: The implementation of PSW aims to increase participation in healthcare and could thus represent a building block for cultural change in healthcare	
Economic effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of (technological and social) innovations, e.g. new/changed: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Business models and economic forms (e.g. shift from profit orientation to public welfare orientation, fair trade) ▪ Goods or products (e.g. recyclable materials) ▪ Business and production processes (e.g. distribution and logistics, information and communication) 	Possible contribution to further effects: Adoption of recommendations for the implementation of a new professional group, including better remuneration and employment models.	

Dimension: Impact

CRITERIA	EXEMPLARY INDICATORS	APPLICATION	IMPPEER-PSY5
Economic effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Securing livelihoods, i.e. satisfaction of basic needs (e.g. food, energy, housing, mobility, health) • Building or strengthening resilient economic structures, e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Security of supply ▪ Regional value creation ▪ Diversification of products, markets, and business areas ▪ Transparent supply chains ▪ Circular economy • Social responsibility and good governance, e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Fair income distribution ▪ Compliance with employee rights, occupational safety, and health protection 		Potential contribution to further effects: taking up recommendations for the implementation of a new occupational group, including better remuneration and employment models.
Ecological effects			Not applicable due to the subject area
Societal effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Promoting access to, e.g.: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Education ▪ Health services • Improving the quality of life and opportunities, especially for socially disadvantaged groups (e.g. health, well-being and self-care) 		Potential contribution to further effects: Strengthening patient orientation and needs-based psychiatric care through PSW.

2.3 Reflection on the Application of the Guide for Assessment

The application of the guide was possible. Most categories were useful when reflecting on the different effects. Only the outcomes on the topics of material changes and ecological effects were not suitable due to the research topic. Reflecting on and tracking this diversity of dimensions within the project would have required extensive resources.

In our view, this investment of resources would have been worthwhile because it would have sharpened the project's objectives during its implementation and thus possibly increased its practical effectiveness. Although, as described

above, the impact criteria were difficult to apply or evaluate, many of these criteria reflect the arguments of individual or multiple team members for engaging in the project (e.g., the goal of improving the remuneration and working models of PSW* or changing the power relations in psychiatric care). In our view, the contribution to far reaching changes (impact) may reflect the fundamental motivation, in particular of practice partners, to get involved in participatory projects. This makes it all the more difficult to determine whether a project has contributed to achieving these goals, as this requires the activities of other actors and changes in the framework conditions.

3 APPLICATION EXAMPLE FROM TRANSDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ON SUSTAINABLE URBAN DEVELOPMENT

Franziska Ehnert

3.1 Context of the Project "Dresden - City of the Future 2030+"

Duration: 2015-2022

Web: <https://www.ioer.de/en/projects/city-of-the-future>; <https://www.zukunftsstadt-dresden.de/>

Background

Against the backdrop of societal challenges such as climate change, biodiversity loss and social inequality, the "Research and Innovation Agenda City of the Future" of the Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) has focused on topics such as climate adaptation, energy security, social housing, sustainable mobility, health, migration and demographic change (BMBF, 2015a). "Dresden - City of the Future 2030+" was funded as part of the "City of the Future" competition (2015-2022), which the BMBF launched in 2015 as part of this agenda.

Objectives

The aim is to develop interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary research approaches to strengthen cooperation between science and society and to better integrate local knowledge into research processes (BMBF, 2015b, 2015a). Therefore, new governance approaches that support transdisciplinary co-creation and innovation development should be explored. In contrast to traditional governance through hierarchy, "Dresden - City of the Future 2030+" was designed a governance approach based on co-creation. From the perspective of sustainability transitions studies and environmental governance studies, the guiding research question was: How can real-world laboratories and experiments as governance innovations contribute to the transformation of existing social configurations?

Method

Dresden became a real-world laboratory for ten transformation experiments (TE) implemented by civil society actors, the municipality and in cooperation

with research partners. The TE tested social and governance innovations to advance a socio-ecological transformation of society. They addressed a wide range of topics, with eight of them being implemented by citizens and two by the municipality. For example, the TE "Week of the Good Life" attempted to make the Äußere Neustadt district car-free for a week.

The TE "Food Bin" raised awareness of food waste by offering workshops on cooking with leftovers and regional and seasonal foods. The TE "Material Mediation" created a physical and digital platform for the redistribution of materials.

The TE "District Funds and Councils for Sustainable and Active Neighbourhoods" sought to enable citizens to help shape their neighbourhoods by establishing district funds and councils based on the principles of decentralisation and subsidiarity.

The TE "Schools as a Living Spaces created together" has made the schoolyard at the Johanna Primary School more sustainable in a co-creative process involving pupils, teachers and parents.

The co-creation process was designed using various participation and workshop formats:

- Vision development: vision-building workshops
- Concept development and planning of the TE: Project workshops
- Implementation of the TE: reflection workshops.

Data collection and analysis were conducted using qualitative and/or quantitative methods, depending on the discipline.

Consortium

On the other hand, the research consortium formed an interdisciplinary team of researchers from the Leibniz Institute for Ecological Urban and Regional Development and the Dresden University of Technology.

They contributed with various academic backgrounds such as sustainability sciences and sustainability transitions studies, political science, sociology, urban ecology, materials science, traffic psychology, economics and knowledge architecture. On the other hand, the collaborative research approach was implemented through cooperation with the Office of the City of the Future of the City of Dresden and the civil society coordinators of the TE. Both the research assistants and the staff of the Office of the City of the Future and the TE coordinators received financial support.

Output

In addition to scientific publications on the development of an experimental governance approach and the findings of the TE, a vision for Dresden in 2030 was drafted during the participatory process, and the experiences of the implementation process were published in a guide with recommendations for various target groups (societal actors and researchers). We therefore developed a digital Urban Transition Kit (WerkStadtKoffer) in a joint co-creation process involving research partners and social actors (see dissemination of results).

Financial support

Federal Ministry of Education and Research and the City of Dresden.

3.2 Exemplary Operationalisation of the Guide

Dimension: Process Quality

CRITERIA	INDICATORS
Power to act	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Has the power to act been (re)distributed? → Were bottom-up processes possible?
Transparency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Was (limited) scope for action (e.g. due to the type of funding allocation) communicated? → Were expectations communicated (on an ongoing basis)? → Were uncertainties in the level of knowledge and complex interrelationships openly explained during the course of the project?
Adaptability / Iterativity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Was there sufficient room for feedback/exchange/comments? → Were there opportunities to document and reflect on unexpected developments → Did the project offer opportunities for different forms of learning?
Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Was there an attitude that allowed for learning from mistakes?
Dissemination of results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> → Were the requirements of the target groups taken into account in the type of outputs? (target group-appropriate language, formats, scope, relevance to action) → Was there cooperation with representatives of the target group (e.g. multipliers) for the dissemination of results? → Was the dissemination of results actively promoted? (e.g. lectures, references in newsletters, social media) → Were results made permanently freely accessible? (open access, etc.)

Power to act

In "Dresden - City of the Future2030+", the ambivalent and contradictory dynamics of empowerment and disempowerment became apparent. On the one hand, co-creation opened up new opportunities for participation and co-creating local transformation processes. On the other hand, the complex, opaque structures and processes within the municipality (functional differentiation), which require a high level of professionalism to communicate and implement one's own concerns, resulted in experiences of disempowerment among societal actors (Ehnert 2025).

Transparency

Particularly for the TE "Week of the Good Life", uncertainties regarding the legal situation for conducting a traffic experiment were not communicated transparently at an early stage (Ehnert 2025).

Discussions with the TE on the legal requirements for a traffic experiment were put on hold by the municipality for a long time because the road traffic regulations were being reformed by the federal government at the time of implementation, and the legal basis for traffic experiments was therefore uncertain to local stakeholders. This lack of transparency led to considerable uncertainty among those involved in the TE and made it almost impossible for them to actively participate in discussions about the risks they were prepared to take in the experimental process. This raises relevant questions of research ethics.

Adaptability/Iterativity

Regular coordination meetings were held between the TE teams and the research partners. Furthermore, reflection workshops were held every six months during the experimental phase to support exchange between all teams and research partners as well as reflection and learning processes in order to synthesise the findings from different TEs. These reflection workshops served as a basis for iteratively adapting the design of the research project, identifying the needs of the TE and developing appropriate formats, e.g. workshops for the continuation and institutionalisation of the TE.

Cooperation

The participants had different expectations regarding the idea of 'learning-by-failing'. For some, their own commitment was also intended to lead to the 'success' of the experiment. For other societal actors and the research partners, the innovative character of the research project lay precisely in its culture of exploration and experimentation. For them, it was important to develop new spaces for 'learning-by-failing' and thus contribute to a cultural change in society.

Dissemination of results

In a co-creation process, research partners and societal actors jointly developed a digital Urban Transition Kit (WerkStadtKoffer). The kit is available with open access.

The format of a digital platform was chosen in order to integrate various formats such as guidelines, video tutorials, graphics and living documents, thereby appealing to different target groups (e.g. actors from civil society, public authorities, business and academia). The individual contents of the UrbanTransitionKit were designed and created in collaboration with societal and research partners. Central questions such as objectives, target groups, suitable formats and contents for the respective elements were discussed jointly. The societal partners also act as multipliers, communicating the contents of the UrbanTransitionKits to their respective communities and thus supporting the knowledge transfer to different communities and contexts.

Dimension: Outcome

CRITERIA	INDICATORS
Promotion of learning processes (cognitive, normative)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target knowledge (normative) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Common understanding of guiding principles and visions for the future ▪ Change in attitudes, values and preferences • Transformation knowledge (actionable knowledge): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Mutual learning: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Development of a common understanding of options for action in the respective field of research ▪ Capacity building: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – e.g. skills for reflection and co-creation of knowledge, learning TDPR methods
Strengthening social relationships and cooperation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Community building and development of collective identities
Emotional changes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Experience of self-efficacy (e.g. change in self-image and self-esteem)
Institutional changes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Temporary) institutional changes (e.g. new positions, areas of responsibilities)

Promoting learning processes (cognitive, normative)

Through joint vision-building, problem understandings were critically questioned and guiding principles for a sustainable development of Dresden were drafted (target knowledge).

The TEs have developed social innovations that aim to promote a paradigm shift from efficiency to sufficiency and from economic growth to post-growth. This contrasts with the concept of ecological modernisation, which reproduces the growth paradigm and seeks to bring about transformation through technological innovation (Ehnert 2025). For example, the TE "Week of the Good Life" encouraged critical dialogue and reflection about "good living" in neighbourhoods and communities. It emphasised that all activities and events during the "Week of the Good Life" should be non-commercial in nature, thereby ensuring inclusion and accessibility for all (Ehnert 2025). In doing so, it sought to create

a counterexample to the commercialisation of public space. Furthermore, the TEs opened up opportunities for disrupting everyday practices and trying out new, sustainable practices, e.g. practices of democratic participation in neighbourhoods (TE "District Funds and Councils for Sustainable and Active Neighbourhoods"), which gave rise to various cognitive and normative learning processes (Batz and Ehnert 2023). The methods for designing and facilitating a co-creation process with citizens in local communities were documented and published in the UrbanTransitionKit (WerkStadtKoffer) to strengthen capacity building.

Strengthening social relationships and cooperation

The TEs "District Funds and Councils for sustainable and active neighbourhoods" and "Schools as a Living Spaces created together" have strengthened community building in the urban districts of Johannstadt and Pieschen-Süd/Mickten and at the primary school "Johanna", as well as identification with the respective neighbourhood and a sense of belonging to "Johanna" (Batz and Ehnert 2023).

Emotional changes

Emotional experiences were rather ambivalent. On the one hand, the BMBF's research funding was perceived as an opportunity and potential for developing social innovations and for participating in and actively shaping local transformation processes that enable people to experience self-efficacy. On the other hand, the projectification through short-term funding programmes was criticised as a challenge to the continuation of one's own commitment and the shaping of long-term societal transformations (Ehnert 2025).

Institutional changes

The Office of the City of the Future was established in the mayor's office of the city of Dresden as a new, intermediary organisational unit that acts as a mediator and translator between civil society and the municipality (Ehnert 2023).

Dimension: Impact

CRITERIA	INDICATORS
Continuation and expansion of activities and practices	<p>In the project context:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Follow-up projects (from own resources or via funding bodies)
Expansion and deepening of cooperation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of new networks and communities of practice (e.g. science-society networks)
Change in knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integration of knowledge into practices, research, teaching and practical infrastructures, institutions, and discourses
Establishment of new/changed institutions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of new/changed organisational units (e.g. sustainability department, prevention department) • Establishment of new/changed role profiles and forms of expertise (e.g. positions, facilitators, knowledge brokers, change in the understanding of the role of science as an institution)
Ecological effects	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resource and energy efficiency (e.g. waste prevention, recycling, durability and reparability of products)

Continuation and expansion of activities and practices

Many of the TE have secured further funding from other sources to continue their activities. For example, "Schools as Living Spaces Created Together" was continued as "Schoolyards Transformers" with funding from the City of Dresden.

Expansion and deepening of cooperation

The TE "Material Mediation Dresden" has committed itself to establishing a Germany-wide network of material initiatives to promote the exchange of experience and knowledge transfer.

Change in knowledge

The research partners have integrated transdisciplinary research approaches and, in particular, real-world laboratories into the module "Spatial Development Project" in the study program "Spatial Development and Natural Resource Management" at the Dresden University of Technology. To anchor this institutionally, the module description has been reformulated.

Establishment of new/changed institutions

The Office of the City of the Future was continued by the City of Dresden as an organisational unit within the mayor's office beyond the project period. It acts as a facilitator between civil society and the municipality.

In this way, the new role profile of a facilitator was established in the municipal administration (Ehnert 2023; Ehnert 2025).

Ecological effects

The TE "Material Mediation", which offers a physical and digital platform for the redistribution of materials, and the TE "The Food Bin", which is dedicated to various event formats to advance prevention of food waste, contribute to increasing resource efficiency. For example, "The Food Bin" has so far been able to save 2,190 kg of food (The Food Bin 2025).

Particularly, the more far reaching impact of the project "Dresden - City of the Future 2030+" can only be evaluated to a limited extent at this stage. On the one hand, the empirical data collection and analysis were conducted within the project period (2019 to 2022) and do not provide sufficient data for considering medium and long-term impacts. These could only be captured through future data collection. On the other hand, there is a problem of attribution, i.e. it is often not possible to trace the contribution of single research projects to overarching effects as these usually arise from the interaction of many actors and different system dynamics.

3.3 Reflection on the Application of the Guide for Assessment

The guide for assessment can support the design, implementation and evaluation of a transdisciplinary research project. The dimension "process quality" poses critical and constructive questions about the design and structure of co-creative research processes for creating an equal footing in the collaboration between research and societal partners. These guiding questions can be used continuously throughout the research process to reflect on and adapt the process design.

For the evaluation of the research project all criteria and indicators of process quality, outcomes and impacts can be applied to "Dresden - City of the Future 2030+". However, the evaluation of impact criteria such as economic or ecological effects requires cooperation with specific disciplines such as economics, urban ecology or material science. The conceptualisation and operationalisation of social constructs such as power relations can also pose a methodological challenge. Different forms of power (e.g. structural or discursive power) would have to be specified for this purpose.

OUTLOOK, REFERENCES AND LITERATURE

The guide for assessment was developed within the AG Wirkung (Impact Working Group) of the Society for Transdisciplinary and Participatory Research (GTPF) as the result of an exchange between transdisciplinary and participatory researchers in various fields of research.

Since the focus of the guide is on reflecting and systematising different societal effects, exchange – especially on perceived usefulness – is very important to us. The guide for assessment will be presented and discussed in various networks in the future. We welcome feedback on whether it is useful for operationalising criteria and indicators

for the evaluation of transdisciplinary and participatory research and where there is a need for further development.

We are also very open to exchange with funding bodies and project sponsors. As sensible as it may be in the coming years to gain a better impression of the societal effects of transdisciplinary and participatory research, it can have ambivalent effects if certain outcomes are prescribed by research funding bodies given the wide range of research forms and objectives. We would be happy to engage in dialogue on how this tension can be addressed.

THE IMPACT WORKING GROUP IN THE GTPF

The present guide covers only a small part of the questions around the topic of societal effects of transdisciplinary and participatory research. The Impact Working Group is working in other subgroups to examine the effects of this type of research in science and how impact-oriented project management can be strengthened. In addition to time-limited work on specific topics and products, we regularly organise public digital discussion events in this field. We are therefore always open to new members who would like to contribute ideas for future questions on the topic

of impact. The meetings of the Impact Working Group, which take place approximately every six months, are ideal for this purpose.

Contacts: For more information about the German speaking Impact Working Group and contact persons, please turn to: <https://gtpf.science/arbeitsgruppen/ag-wirkung.html>

Contact for the Guide for Assessment Product Group: Martina Schäfer (schaefer@ztg.tu-berlin.de)

THE SOCIETY FOR TRANSDISCIPLINARY AND PARTICIPATORY RESEARCH (GTPF)

The Society for Transdisciplinary and Participatory Research (GTPF) is the professional association for transdisciplinary and participatory researchers, teachers and practice partners in German-speaking countries.

The GTPF offers a central platform for networking, professional exchange and representation of interests in the field of transdisciplinary and participatory research, as well as for cooperation between science and society.

The goals of the society are:

- Networking of transdisciplinary and participatory researchers in German-speaking countries,
- Promoting young scientists,
- Professionalising, consolidating and establishing transdisciplinary and participatory research and teaching,
- Representing the interests of the community of transdisciplinary and participatory researchers in Germany.

Further information, including details of the various working groups, can be found at <https://gtpf.science/>

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